

Application of the Mannich Reaction to Some Coumarin Derivatives

M. G. Patel and S. Sethna

6 & 7-Hydroxycoumarins, 7-hydroxy-3-ethoxycarbonylcoumarin, and 6-bromo derivative of the latter have been subjected to the Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and dimethylamine, benzylamine, and aniline. The structures of the alkylamino- and oxazino-coumarin derivatives obtained have been established by converting them into compounds of known structures.

Robertson and Link¹ subjected 4-hydroxycoumarin to the Mannich reaction. Recently Desai² has studied the application of this reaction to some 4-methylcoumarin derivatives. Gupta *et al.*^{3a} have synthesised Mannich bases from umbelliferone and 4-methylumbelliferone and found them to be powerful nervous system and respiratory stimulants. The application of this reaction to 6- and 7-hydroxycoumarins and 7-hydroxy-3-ethoxycarbonylcoumarin and its 6-bromo derivative has now been studied.

7-Hydroxycoumarin by the interaction of one mole of paraformaldehyde and dimethylamine furnished the 8-dimethylaminomethyl derivative which gave the known 8-formyl derivative³ on reaction with hexamethylenetetramine. Reaction with one mole of formaldehyde and benzylamine furnished two products: (i) an alkali-soluble product which was assigned the 8-benzylaminomethyl structure as it gave the above mentioned 8-formyl derivative by reaction with hexamethylenetetramine; (ii) an alkali-insoluble product which was assigned 2'-H-3'-benzyl-3',4'-dihydro-1',3'-oxazino-5',6'-8,7-coumarin (Ia) structure⁴. With boiling hydrochloric acid the latter gave the 8-benzylaminomethyl derivative and formaldehyde. For similar reasons, the products from the Mannich reaction of 7-hydroxycoumarin with formaldehyde and aniline have been assigned the 8-anilino-methyl and 2'-H-3'-phenyl-3',4'-dihydro-1',3'-oxazino-5',6'-8,7-coumarin (Ib) structures.

6-Hydroxycoumarin with formaldehyde and dimethylamine furnished the 5-dimethylaminomethyl derivative which could be converted into the known 5-formyl derivative⁵ on its reaction with hexamethylenetetramine. With benzylamine and aniline, only the oxazino derivatives: 2'-H-3'-benzyl-3',4'-dihydro-1',3'-oxazino-5',6'-5,6-coumarin (IIa) and 2'-H-3'-phenyl-3',4'-dihydro-1',3'-oxazino-5',6'-5,6-coumarin (IIb) respectively were obtained. These on refluxing with hydrochloric acid gave 5-benzylaminomethyl and 5-anilinomethyl-6-hydroxycoumarin respectively. Both gave the same 5-formyl derivative (*vide supra*) on heating with hexamethylenetetramine.

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1883.

2. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 5251.

2a. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 300.

3. Späth and Pailer, *Ber.*, 1935, 68, 941.

4. Cf. Barke, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 600.

5. Naik and Thakor, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 1626.

7-Hydroxy-3-ethoxycarbonylcoumarin on the Mannich reaction with dimethylamine and benzylamine gave 7-hydroxy-3-ethoxycarbonyl-8-dimethylaminomethylcoumarin and 2'-H-3'-benzyl-3', 4'-dihydro-3-ethoxycarbonyl-1', 3'-oxazino-5',6',7'-coumarin respectively. These products on bromination gave monobromo derivatives which were identical with the products obtained on the Mannich reaction between 7-hydroxy-3-ethoxycarbonyl-6-bromocoumarin and dimethylamine and benzylamine respectively, indicating that the condensation had taken place in all cases in the 8-position. Some of the alkylamino derivatives have been converted into the acetoxymethyl derivatives by treatment with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate.

(I)

R = (a) $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; (b) C_6H_5 .

(II)

EXPERIMENTAL*

General Procedure for the Mannich Reaction.—Paraformaldehyde (0.01 or 0.02M) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (5 ml containing 0.01g. of KOH) by gentle warming. The amine (0.01M) was added gradually with cooling followed by the coumarin derivative (0.01M) and absolute ethanol (5 ml) in succession. The reaction mixture was gently heated on a steam bath for 2 hours. The pasty product obtained on keeping overnight was triturated with cold petroleum ether. The paste was then extracted with cold petroleum ether and finally with hot benzene. The product obtained on removal of benzene was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture.

In the case of 6-hydroxycoumarin and 7-hydroxy-3-ethoxycarbonylcoumarin, needles separated on cooling the reaction mixture. These were recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture.

Formylcoumarins.—The aminomethylcoumarin (1g.) was refluxed with acetic acid (10 mf.) and hexamethylenetetramine (2.g.) for 4 hrs. on a low flame. HCl. (conc., 10 ml) was then added and the reaction mixture refluxed further for 1 hr. The solution obtained on adding the reaction mixture to water was extracted with ether and the residue left on removal of ether was crystallised from benzene. The formylcoumarins were directly compared with the compounds synthesised by the method described in the literature.

*All melting points are uncorrected.

6-Hydroxy-5-benzylaminomethylcoumarin.—2'-H-3'-benzyl-3',4'-dihydro-1',3'-oxazino-5',6'-5,6-coumarin (0.5 g.) in ethanol and HCl (5 ml) was distilled and the distillate collected in water (25 ml). During distillation dilute ethanol (1:1, 20 ml) was added to the reaction mixture. The solid that began to separate was dissolved in more ethanol and the solution neutralised with sodium bicarbonate. The product obtained was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in needles, m.p. 128-29°. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 5.4; N, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 72.6; H, 5.4; N, 5.0%). The distillation gave on treatment with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of formaldehyde.

The *hydrochloride* was prepared as usual and crystallised from ethanol-ether mixture, m.p. 222-23°. (Found: C, 64.2; H, 4.8; Cl, 11.0. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3N.HCl$ requires C, 64.2; H, 5.0; Cl, 11.2%).

6-Hydroxy-5-anilinomethylcoumarin.—2'-H-3'-phenyl-3',4'-dihydro-1',3'-oxazino-5',6'-5,6-coumarin (0.5 g.) was treated similarly as the above coumarin and the product was crystallised from absolute ethanol in needles, m.p. 197-98°. (Found: C, 72.0; H, 4.9; N, 5.2. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 71.9; H, 4.9; N, 5.2%).

7-Acetoxy-8-acetoxymethylcoumarin.—7-Hydroxy-8-dimethylaminomethylcoumarin hydrochloride (0.2 g.) was treated with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate on a steam bath for 2 hrs. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in needles, m.p. 128-29°. (Found: C, 61.1; H, 4.5. $C_{14}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 60.87; H, 4.4%).

6-Acetoxy-5-acetoxymethylcoumarin was prepared as above from 6-hydroxy-5-dimethylaminomethylcoumarin and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in needles, m.p. 117-18°. (Found: C, 60.9; H, 4.7. $C_{14}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 60.87; H, 4.4%).

7-Acetoxy-8-(N-acetyl)-benzylaminomethylcoumarin was prepared from 7-hydroxy-8-benzylaminomethylcoumarin as above. The product crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in needles, m.p. 137-38°. (Found: C, 68.9; H, 5.3; N, 3.9. $C_{21}H_{19}O_3N$ requires C, 69.0; H, 5.2; N, 3.8%).

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